

Studies in 3-Hydroxy Coumarins: Part II¹. Synthesis of 3-Hydroxy Pyrano (2, 3-h) Benzopyran and 3-Hydroxy Pyrano (3, 2-g) Benzopyran Derivatives

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7-Hydroxy-8-formyl-4-methylcoumarin when condensed with acetyl glycine in presence of sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, gave 3-acetamido-8-methyl-2-6-dioxo-2H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran, which when refluxed with 70% sulphuric acid gave 3-amino derivative. This when treated with sodium nitrite and concentrated sulphuric acid afforded 3-hydroxy-8-methyl-2-6-dioxo-2H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran (Ic). 3-Hydroxy-2,6-dioxo-2H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h) benzopyran (Id) and 4-methyl-7,10-dihydroxy-2,8-dioxo-2H,8H-pyrano(3,2-g) benzopyran (IIc) were similarly synthesised, from 7-hydroxy-8-formyl-coumarin and 7,8-dihydroxy-6-formyl-4-methylcoumarin respectively.

3-Hydroxycoumarin has an inhibiting effect on growth of avena roots and 3-amino-coumarins which are intermediates in the synthesis of 3-hydroxycoumarins, are found to have antibacterial activity against Staphylococcus Pyrogens, Salmonella, Shigella etc. Trivedi and Sethna¹ synthesised different 3-hydroxycoumarin derivatives and studied the pattern of substitution in 3-hydroxycoumarin. It was therefore thought of interest to extend this work for the synthesis of 3-hydroxypyran(2,3-h)benzopyran and 3-hydroxypyran(3,2-g)benzopyran derivatives.

a : R : NHCOCH ₃	R ₁ : CH ₃	a : R : NHCOCH ₃	R ₁ : OCOCH ₃
b : R : NH ₂	R ₁ : CH ₃	b : R : NH ₂	R ₁ : OH
c : R : OH	R ₁ : CH ₃	c : R : R ₁ : OH	
d : R : OH	R ₁ : CH ₃		

1. K. N. Trivedi and S. Sethna, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 1817.

7-Hydroxy-8-formyl-4-methylcoumarin was condensed according to Shaw *et al.*² with acetyl glycine in presence of sodium acetate and acetic anhydride to give 3-acetamido-8-methyl-2,6-dioxo-2H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran (Ia), which when refluxed with 70% sulphuric acid gave 3-amino derivative (Ib). (Ib) could not be converted to (Ic) when refluxed with hydrochloric acid and so it was diazotised with sodium nitrite and sulphuric acid. The diazotised solution, when heated with sulphuric acid at 40°, afforded 3-hydroxy-8-methyl-2,6-dioxo-2H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran (Ic). It developed green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution which is characteristic of 3-hydroxycoumarins.

7-Hydroxy-8-formylcoumarin on similar series of reactions gave 3-hydroxy-2,6-dioxo-2H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran (Id).

7,8-Dihydroxy-6-formyl-4-methylcoumarin⁴ on condensation with acetyl glycine in the presence of acetic anhydride and sodium acetate gave 4-methyl-7-acetamido-10-acetoxy-2,8-dioxo-2H,8H-pyrano(3,2-h)benzopyran (IIa). (IIa) on refluxing with 70% sulphuric acid gave 4-methyl-7-amino-10-hydroxy-2,8-dioxo-2H,8H-pyrano(2,3-g)benzopyran (IIb). This on diazotisation and heating with sulphuric acid at 40–50° gave 7,10-dihydroxy-4-methyl-2,8-dioxo-2H,8H-pyrano(3,2-g) benzopyran (IIc).

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Acetamido-8-methyl-2,6-dioxo-2H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran (Ia): 7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-8-formylcoumarin³ (1 g.) and acetyl glycine (1 g.) mixed with anhydrous sodium acetate (1.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 ml.) are heated at 140–50° in an oil bath for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was poured in ice and the product separated was treated with very dilute sodium hydroxide to remove unreacted starting product. The insoluble product crystallised from acetic acid as pinkish crystalline needles, m.p. 311°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 62.7; H, 3.86; N, 4.86%. C₁₅H₁₁O₅N requires C, 63.17; H, 3.86; N, 4.91%).

3-Amino-8-methyl-2,6-dioxo-2H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran (Ib): (Ia) (0.5 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid and refluxed with 70% sulphuric acid (4 ml.) in water bath for 2 to 3 hr. The clear solution was slowly poured in ice cold ammonia. The crude product was purified by dissolving in hydrochloric acid and reprecipitated by ammonia and was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 285°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 64.45; H, 3.89; N, 5.67%. C₁₃H₉O₄N requires C, 64.19; H, 3.70; N, 5.76%).

3-Hydroxy-8-methyl-2,6-dioxo-2H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran (Ic): (Ib) (0.8 g.) was dissolved in minimum quantity of acetic acid (10 ml.) and 4 ml. of con. sulphuric acid was added. The reaction mixture was cooled below 0°C and then cold solution of sodium nitrite (1 g. in 10 ml. water) was added drop by drop with constant stirring. The reaction was stirred further for 20–30 minutes at 0°. The yellow solution was then poured in 10% sulphuric acid (10 ml.) at 40° and kept at this temperature for 15 minutes. The separated product was filtered, washed with hydrochloric acid (1 : 1) and crystallised from acetic acid,

2. K. N. F. Shaw, A. McMillen and M. D. Armstrong, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, **21**, 601.
3. S. Rangaswami and T. R. Seshadri, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1937, **6A**, 112.
4. V. M. Thakore and R. M. Naik, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, **22**, 1629.

m.p. 292°. Yield 0.2 g. It developed characteristic green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution and was soluble in sodium hydroxide solution in cold. (Found : C, 63.69; H, 3.7%. $C_{13}H_8O_5$ requires C, 63.93; H, 3.27%).

3-Acetamido-2,6-dioxo-2H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran : 7-Hydroxy-8-formylcoumarin⁵ (1 g.), acetyl glycine (1 g.) and fused sodium acetate (1.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 ml.) were mixed and heated at 150° for 7 hr. in an oil bath. The reaction mixture was poured in ice-cold water, the product was purified by treating with 3% sodium hydroxide solution and crystallised from acetic acid as yellow crystals, m.p. 308°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 62.34; H, 3.13; N, 4.66%. $C_{14}H_9O_5N$ requires C, 61.98; H, 3.32; N, 5.16%).

3-Amino-2,6-dioxo-2H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran : 3-Acetamido-2,6-dioxo-2H, 6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran (0.5 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid and was refluxed with 70% sulphuric acid in water bath for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was poured in ice-cold ammonia solution and the separated product crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 296. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 63.03; H, 3.28; N, 6.43%. $C_{12}H_7O_4N$ requires C, 62.90; H, 3.03; N, 6.11%).

3-Hydroxy-2,6-dioxo-2H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran (Id) : 3-Amino-2,6-dioxo-2H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran was dissolved in acetic acid (0.5 g. in 10 ml.), 4 ml. of conc. sulphuric acid was added. The mixture was cooled to 0° and then cold solution of sodium nitrite (10%; 10 ml.) was added dropwise with stirring. The yellow solution was poured in 10% sulphuric acid at 40° and kept at this temperature for 15 minutes. The separated product was washed with hydrochloric acid (1 : 1). It was further purified by passing over alumina and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 235°. It developed characteristic green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 62.3; H, 2.6%. $C_{12}H_6O_5$ requires C, 62.6; H, 3.1%).

4-Methyl-7-acetamido-10-acetoxy-2,8-dioxo-2H,8H-pyrano(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIa) : A mixture of 7,8-dihydroxy-6-formyl-4-methylcoumarin⁴ (1 g.) and acetyl glycine (1.5 g.) and anhydrous sodium acetate (2.0 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 ml.) was heated in an oil bath at 140–50° for 10 hr. The reaction was worked out as before. The separated product crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow needles, m.p. 320°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found : C, 60.03; H, 3.77; N, 3.97%. $C_{17}H_{13}O_7N$ requires C, 59.47; H, 3.78; N, 4.08%).

4-Methyl-7-amino-10-hydroxy-2,8-dioxo-2H,8H-pyrano(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIb) : (IIa) (0.5 g.) was dissolved in minimum quantity of acetic acid and refluxed with 10 ml. 70% sulphuric acid in a water bath for 3 hrs. and was poured in cold dilute ammonia solution. The product after purification by usual treatment was crystallised from nitrobenzene, m.p. 345°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 60.10; H, 3.44; N, 5.97%. $C_{13}H_9O_5N$ requires C, 60.23; H, 3.47; N, 5.40%).

4-Methyl-7,10-dihydroxy-2,8-dioxo-2H,8H-pyrano(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIc) : (IIb) (1.0 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (10 ml.) and conc. sulphuric acid was added (10 ml.). The mixture was cooled below 0° and cold solution of sodium nitrite (2 g. in 10 ml. water) was added dropwise with stirring. It was kept cooled and stirred for 30 minutes and then poured in

10% sulphuric acid (10 ml.) at 40-50° and kept at this temperature for 15 minutes. The separated product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 209-10°. Yield 0.2 g. It developed [characteristic green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution and was soluble in sodium hydroxide in cold. (Found : C, 59.50; H, 3.42%. $C_{31}H_8O_6$ requires C, 59.99; H, 3.07%).

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